

NUTRIENT COMPOSITION AND ACCEPTABILITY OF SOY-FORTIFIED CUSTARD

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ABSTRACT

The proximate composition and characteristics of custard formulation fortified with soybean flour were studied. The corn starch (CS) was composite with soybean flour (SF) at the levels of 10%, 20%, 30%, 40% and 50%. The custard formulations prepared from the flour blends were evaluated for their proximate composition and sensory characteristics. From the results, the protein content of the formulations increased steadily with increasing supplementation of soybean flour from 10.65% in 90:10 (CS : SF) to 17.16% in 50:50 (CS : SF) samples, while the carbohydrate decreased. Conversely, the energy content of the formulations decreased as the level of fortification with soybean flour increased from 360.50KJ in 50:50 (CS: SF) to 373.78KJ in 90:10 (CS : SF). The sensory evaluation performed on different samples of custard formulation after reconstitution into gruel with boiling water showed that the formulation fortified with 10% soybean flour was the most acceptable because there was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between this sample and the control, (Custard formulation were significantly different ($p > 0.05$) from the control, with the formulation fortified with 50% soybean flour having the lowest over all acceptability.

KEYWORDS: Custard, Corn starch, soybean flour, fortification, quality assessment.

INTRODUCTION

Custard is a fine textured food product made from corn starch in which salt, flavouring and colouring agents are added with or without the addition of egg yolk solids, vitamins and minerals. The corn starch used for the preparation of custard is basically a dense, powery flour obtained from the endosperm protein of the corn kernel. Custard is primarily consumed either as a breakfast cereal-based food or weaning food in most developing nations of the tropics especially among children (Ihekoronye and Ngoddy, 1985). Since custard is mainly rich in carbohydrate, there is need to improve the nutritional status of the product by the addition of vegetable proteins from oilseeds and legumes such as cowpea, soybean and pigeon pea etc, which are relatively cheap and readily available. The fortification of custard with vegetable proteins from oilseeds and legumes has received considerable attention. This is because oilseed and legume proteins are high in lysine, an essential limiting amino acid in most cereals (Enwere, 1998). Legumes generally contain relatively high amount of protein should complement the protein in cereal grains because the chemical and nutritional characteristics of legumes make them natural complements to cereal-based diets (MARero *et al*, 1988).

Soybean (*Glycine max*) a grain legume, is one of the richest and cheapest sources of plant protein that can be used to improve the diets of millions of people, especially the poor and low income earners in developing countries because of its nutritional quality, attractiveness and functional properties (Iwe, 2003).

Soybeans is mainly cultivated for its seeds which are used commercially as human food, livestock feed and for the extraction of oil.

Nutritionally, soybean protein resembles animal protein more closely than other vegetable proteins from oilseeds and legumes. Soybean protein constitutes about 40% of the total solids and plays a very important role in the enrichment of cereal-based food products (Fukushima, 1999). It is also a rich source of vitamin, minerals and is relatively low in crude fibre (Duke, 1981). Soybean is one such protein sources, which

when used partially to replace or complement corn starch in the preparation of custard would help tremendously in improving the nutritional quality of the product. The objective of this study was to examine the chemical composition and consumers' acceptability of custard formulations fortified with different proportions of soybean flour.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

White variety of maize (*Zea mays*) and soybean (*Glycine max*) used for this study were purchased from a local market in Owerri, Nigeria.

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Preparation of Corn Starch

The corn starch was prepared according to the method described by Ihekoronye and Ngoddy (1985) as shown in Figure 1. During preparation, two kilograms of maize grains which were free from dirt and other foreign materials such as stones, sticks and leaves were weighed and cracked (attrition mill) into grits. The grits obtained were soaked in tap water for 24 hours with occasional change of water at intervals of 6 hours to prevent fermentation. Thereafter, the steeped grits were drained and wet milled (attrition mill) with warm water into fine slurry. The resulting starch slurry was filtered or sieved (muslin cloth) and allowed to sediment for 3 hours. The filtered and sedimented starch was decanted, dewatered and dried in the cabinet dryer (65°C, 6h). After that, the dried starch was milled (attrition mill) and sieved to pass through a 400 mesh sieve. The corn starch produced was finally packaged in sealed polyethylene bags for blending and preparation of custard formulations.

Preparation of Defatted Soybean Flour

The defatted soybean flour was prepared according to the method described by Okaka (1997) as shown in Figure 2.

During preparation, two kilograms of soybean seeds which were free from foreign particles such as stones, sticks and leaves were weighed, cleaned, dried in the cabinet dryer (65°C, 1h), and soaked in tap water for 8 hours. After that, the soaked seeds were cleaned, dehulled manually, boiled (100°C, 30min) and dried further in the cabinet dryer (65°C, 12h). During drying, the dehulled seeds were stirred at intervals of 30 minutes to ensure uniform drying. The dried seeds were milled (attrition mill) and the resulting flour was defatted using 1000ml of n-hexane in soxhlet extractor for the period of 8 hours. Thereafter, the defatted soybean flour produced was dried in the cabinet dryer (68°C, 2h), cooled, and sieved to pass through a 400 mesh sieve. The defatted soybean flour obtained was finally packaged in sealed polythene bags for blending and preparation of custard formulations.

Preparation of Custard Formulations

The custard formulations were prepared according to the method described by Ikohoronye (1999) as shown in Figure 3. During preparation, the corn starch (CS) was composite with soybean flour (SF) at the levels 10%, 20%, 30%, 40% and 50% in a kenwood mixer (Model A 900) to obtain various samples of corn starch/soybean flour blend. After blending, 15% egg yolk, 10% vanilla flavour and 2% salt were added to each of the flour blends and mixed thoroughly in a kenwood mixer (Model A 220) for 10mins to produce fortified custard formulations.

Thereafter, the fortified custard formulations produced were individually packaged in sealed polyethylene bags and kept at room temperature until used for analysis. In addition, 100% corn starch custard formulation was similarly prepared as reference. The various samples of custard formulation produced from CS/SF blends are shown in Table 1.

Chemical Analysis

The moisture, protein, fat, ash and fibre contents of each of the custard formulations were determined in triplicates according to the methods of AOAC (1990). The carbohydrate was determined by difference (Cort *et al.*, 1986). The food energy was calculated from proximate composition according to the standard method described by Passmore and Eastwood (1986).

Sensory Evaluation

The custard made from 100% corn starch and the fortified samples with various levels of supplementation with defatted soybean flour were prepared into different samples of gruel with boiling water. During preparation, 20g of each of the samples was suspended with 100ml of tap water in a small plastic bowl. Thereafter, 80ml of boiling water was added to each of the suspended sample to produce hot gruel. After preparation, a teaspoonful of sucrose was added to each of the samples to improve its taste. The samples of gruel produced were scored by a panel of twenty untrained judges drawn from the University Community for attributes of colour, flavour, texture and general acceptability on a hedonic scale of 1-9 where 1 = dislike extremely and 9 = like extremely (Ihekoronye and Ngoddy, 1985).

Statistical Analysis

The means and standard deviations of all the analyses were calculated. The results were subjected to analysis of variance to detect significant differences ($P < 0.05$) among the sample values. The turkey test was used in separating significant means.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proximate composition of custard formulations prepared from corn starch/soybean flour blends are shown in Table 2. The moisture content of the custard formulations ranged from 6.14% to 6.72%. The differences could be attributed to inadequate drying of maize grains and soybean seed after soaking during processing. The protein content of all the formulations was significantly different from each other ($P < 0.05$). The custard formulations prepared from blends with higher concentrations of soybean flour contained more protein than the formulations made from blends containing less proportion of soybean flour. The result showed that soybeans are good sources of protein. (Salunkhe *et al.*, 1992). The fat content of the formulations was generally higher than those previously reported for custard products. The increase in fat content of all the formulations could be due to insufficient extraction of oil from the soybean flour during the defatting process.

However, soybeans have been reported to be good sources of fat (NAS, 1979). The ash and fibre contents of the formulations were significantly different from each other. The ash and fibre contents of the formulations increased steadily as the level of soybean flour inclusion increased.

The results of the ash and fibre contents of the formulations are generally in agreement with those reported by Abrahamsson *et al.*, (1978). The carbohydrate content of the formulations decreased gradually with increasing content of soybean flour. The result indicated that soybean is not good sources of carbohydrate (Iwe, 2003). The energy content of the custard formulations ranged from 360.58KJ/100g to 376.45KJ/100g. There was significant difference in the energy content of the formulations ($P < 0.05$). The energy content of the formulations was higher than those reported by Brian and Allan (1982).

The scores of the sensory evaluation performed on samples of gruel prepared from CS/SF blended custard formulations after reconstitution are show in Table 3. The scores of various sensory attributes were low in all the samples of gruel prepared from the different formulations. However, the of gruel prepared from the formulation produced from 100% corn starch (sample A) used as control was most acceptable by the judges and was also significantly different ($p < 0.05$) from the other samples in colour, flavour and texture.

The differences could be due to the unique quality of corn starch in the preparation of cereal-based food formulations (Oke, 1975).

Fig. 2: Flow chart for the production of defatted soybean flour.

The fortification of custard formulations with soybean flour up to 40% produced good results. Acceptable results were also reported for maize / cowpea flour blended weaning food formulations (Akobundu and Hoskins, 1987).

CONCLUSION

Custard formulations of acceptable quality relative to those made from corn starch were produced from corn starch / soybean flour blends. The substitution of corn starch (CS) with soybean flour (SF) up to 40% produced good results. From the findings of this study, it was observed that the custard formulation fortified with soybean flour had better nutritional quality than the formulation prepared from 100% corn starch because of their high protein, ash and fibre contents. The fortification of custard formulations with soybean flour could help to alleviate the problem of malnutrition prevalent in the rural areas of our society especially among children. Further studies should be performed on the fortified custard formulations to evaluate their respective shelf life and protein quality.

Fig. 3: Flow chart for the fortified custard production.

Table 1: Samples of Custard Formulation

Samples	CS (%)	SF(%)
A	100	0
B	90	10
C	80	20
D	70	30
E	60	40
F	50	50

Table 2: Means ^{1,2} of proximate composition of custard formulations prepared from CS and CS: SF Blends on dry weight basis.

Samples	Moisture (%)	Protein (%)	Fat (%)	Ash (%)	Fibre (%)	Carbohydrate (%)	Energy KJ/100g
A	8.02 ^a	0.85 ^a	2.05 ^a	0.43 ^a	2.75 ^a	86.68 ^a	376.44 ^a
B	1.14 ^b	10.65 ^b	3.14 ^b	4.34 ^b	3.20 ^b	76.64 ^b	373.76 ^b
C	6.22 ^c	12.18 ^c	3.24 ^c	5.22 ^c	3.88 ^c	75.25 ^c	370.44 ^c
D	6.34 ^d	14.02 ^d	3.64 ^d	5.48 ^d	4.02 ^d	72.32 ^d	370.14 ^d
E	6.50 ^e	16.08 ^e	4.64 ^e	5.62 ^e	4.26 ^e	68.76 ^e	368.26 ^e
F	6.72 ^f	17.16 ^f	4.82 ^f	6.02 ^f	4.62 ^f	63.84 ^f	360.54 ^f

1. Values are means of triplicate samples
2. Means in the same column and followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other (p>0.05)

Table 3: Means ^{1,2} of sensory evaluation performed on samples of reconstituted custard gruel prepared from CS and CS:SF Blends

Samples	Colour	Flavour	Texture	General acceptability
A	4.2a	7.4a	6.8a	8.4a
B	4.8b	6.8a	6.4b	7.6a
C	5.4c	6.6c	6.2c	7.0c
D	6.0d	5.6c	6.0b	5.6d
E	6.6e	4.8d	5.4c	4.8c
F	7.2f	4.2e	4.6d	4.4e

1. Values are means of 20 untrained judges
2. Means in the same column and followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other (p>0.05)

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